

Formidlingsaktivitet

Art: STEAM / STEM science communication / SDU-Galaxy Fysikkubber i Region Syddanmark.

Sted: Svendborg

Skole: Svendborg Gymnasium; 1.g / 2.g / 3.g

Dato: 02. november 2023

Tid: 14:00 – 17:00

Antal elever: ca. 8 students.

GDPR / pictures for public? Yes. Permission obtained.

Lærerkontakt: Rune & Mads

Formidler: Tobias C. Hinse (Syddansk Universitet, FKF / SDU / SDU-Galaxy).

